

EVOLUTION OF HUMAN VALUES ACROSS AGE GROUPS IN BENGALI TEXTBOOKS OF WEST BENGAL : A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PRE AND POST 2011 CURRICULUM

Dr. Anup Biswas

Assistant Professor, Sevayatan Sikshan Mahavidyalaya, Jhargram,
West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Human values encompass both widely accepted social norms and the expected behavior of individuals. For school children, these values play a crucial role in helping them adapt to their environment while shaping their emotional and moral development. Textbooks, beyond enhancing cognitive skills, serve as a fundamental tool in instilling these values. In 2011, a political shift in West Bengal led to major educational reforms, including changes in the elementary school curriculum. As a result, the content of vernacular Bengali textbooks before and after 2011 reflects notable differences. Some values have remained consistent, while others have evolved to align with contemporary educational priorities. This study examines the evolution in human values across different age groups in Bengali textbooks, focusing on how value representation has changed due to curriculum revisions. A qualitative content analysis was conducted on sixteen Bengali textbooks — eight from the pre-2011 curriculum and eight from the post-2011 curriculum, covering Classes I to VIII under the West Bengal Board of primary Education (WBBPE). The study employed a coding approach to categorize and analyze values such as aesthetic expression, environmental awareness, national consciousness, empathy, truthfulness, self-confidence, learning to live together, and love for family. The findings reveal a significant shift in the distribution and emphasis of values in newer textbooks. While traditional values like dignity of labor and religious tolerance were more prominent in older textbooks, newer textbooks place greater emphasis on cooperation, democratic decision-making, gender equality, and positive thinking. Additionally, national consciousness and environmental awareness have received increased focus in both textbook versions.

Keywords: Age Group, Bengali Textbooks, Evolution, Human Values

INTRODUCTION

The Evolution of Value Education in Bengali Textbooks

The integration of value education into Bengali literature has been a longstanding tradition, with textbooks serving as a primary tool for instilling moral principles. Institutions like Fort William College and the Serampore Baptist Mission played a pivotal role in incorporating ethical teachings into early educational materials. According to Khastagir (2004), Bengali prose has historically been a key medium for transmitting moral education, particularly among young learners. Given the fragmented structure of Hindu society, divided by caste and sectarian divisions, moral instruction became essential for fostering unity and ethical awareness.

Over time, value education gained prominence in textbooks, reflecting a growing societal interest in character development. From the establishment of Fort William College to Vidyasagar's reforms, vernacular textbooks became a significant means of imparting ethical values. In the post-Vidyasagar era, several Bengali literary works, such as "Sisupathya" by Ramgoti Nayaytarka, "Sikhyasnobisher Podya" by Akshoykumar Dutta, "Hasi-Khusi" (1904), "Adarshapath" (1925), and "Sushiksha" (1926) by Yogindranath Sarkar, played a crucial role in shaping moral education.

A significant transformation occurred with Rabindranath Tagore's contributions to Bengali literature, particularly through "Sahaj Path" (1930). His work introduced a harmonious blend of language, artistic expression, and moral instruction, offering a more engaging and thought-provoking approach to value education. In 1981, the West Bengal Board of Secondary Education introduced "Kishalay," a textbook specifically designed to promote ethical values among young learners. Before incorporating it into the curriculum, committees and education experts carefully evaluated its content, ensuring a structured approach to value integration. Instead of directly stating moral lessons, values were subtly embedded within literary narratives, allowing students to develop an intrinsic sense of ethics.

Post 2011 Reforms and Their Impact on Value Education

Following West Bengal's political transition in 2011, the newly elected government introduced significant educational reforms. A draft report on curriculum and course structure emphasized that moral education should not be limited to textbooks alone but should also be incorporated into extracurricular activities and school governance policies. The report highlighted the critical role of teachers in fostering a value-based learning environment.

The period between 1981 and 2011 was crucial for value education, as Bengali literature reached a peak in moral instruction. However, after 2011, a major shift occurred, transitioning from implicit value teaching to explicit moral education within primary school curricula. While Vidyasagar's writings conveyed moral teachings directly, Tagore's approach relied on metaphors, imagery, and symbolism to express ethical ideas. This shift likely reflects the fact that Vidyasagar was deeply involved in social reform, whereas Tagore, as a literary figure, focused on artistic expression and philosophical thought.

Curriculum Restructuring and the New Educational Approach after 2011

In July 2011, a new curriculum committee was established to review and revise the government school syllabus in West Bengal. The committee aimed to align the curriculum with national and global educational standards, incorporating recommendations from the Right to Education Act (2009), the Yashpal Committee, and the National Curriculum Framework (2005). These reforms emphasized "learning without burden," shifting the focus from rote memorization to conceptual understanding.

To modernize the curriculum, textbook content was thematically structured, integrating works by renowned Bengali authors alongside translated texts from global literature. This ensured a broad and diverse moral education that reflected local traditions as well as international perspectives. The committee also recognized that value education should extend beyond textbooks, incorporating creative activities, cultural learning, and historical perspectives to instill patriotism, communal harmony, cultural pride, and good habits in students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of this present study was:

O1 : To examine the evolution of human values across different age groups in Bengali textbooks in elementary level of West Bengal before and after 2011.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive research design to analyze the shifts in human values reflected in Bengali textbooks before and after 2011. The content analysis method was employed to systematically examine and interpret the values embedded in textbooks, focusing on their presence, frequency, and thematic representation. *Primary data were collected from sixteen Bengali textbooks—eight published before 2011 (Kisoloy (Classes I–V), Sahitya Songroho (Class VI), Sahitya Chayan (Class VII), Sahitya Bithi (Class VIII) and eight published after 2011 Amar Boi (Classes I & II), Patabahar (Classes III–V), Sahitya Mela (Classes VI–VIII). Additionally, relevant books, documents, and curriculum reports were reviewed to understand the broader context of value education reforms. The study utilized a coding approach to classify and compare key values, such as aesthetic expression, environmental awareness, national consciousness, empathy, truthfulness, and democratic decision-making. By applying qualitative content analysis, this research identifies patterns in value representation across different age groups, providing insights into how curriculum revisions have influenced moral education in West Bengal's elementary education system.*

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

To analyze the representation of human values in Bengali vernacular textbooks, a qualitative data analysis approach was followed. The procedure included the following steps:

Step 1: Identification of Values

- The study involved a detailed content analysis of Bengali textbooks from Class I to Class VIII (both old and new).
- Human values were identified based on explicit and implicit references in stories, poems, essays, and illustrations.
- The values considered for analysis included such as aesthetic expression, environmental awareness, national consciousness, empathy, truthfulness, quest for knowledge, discipline, self-confidence, learning to live together, and love for family.
- A systematic coding approach was applied to classify and document the presence of these values in each textbook.

Step 2: Positioning and Frequency Analysis

- Each identified value was categorized based on its occurrence in the textbooks.
- The frequency of each value was noted to determine which values were emphasized more in different textbooks.

- A comparative table was created to track how often each value appeared in different class levels and across old and new textbooks.

Step 3: Comparison across Age Groups and Time Periods

- The values reflected in the textbooks were compared across different age groups to examine shifts in emphasis from lower (Class I–V) to upper (Class VI–VIII) elementary levels.
- A comparison was made between old textbooks (pre-2011) and new textbooks (post-2011) to identify trends and changes in the representation of values.
- Any noticeable increase, decrease, or replacement of values was carefully analyzed.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Vernacular Textbooks and Reflected Human Values:

Bengali textbooks convey a wide range of values through poems, prose, rhymes, theatre, music, and essays. This research focuses on expert-recommended values that were selected for inclusion in elementary-level vernacular textbooks. According to Biswas, Sinha, and Guha (2018), a total of 54 values were identified as essential for elementary education. These values include:

- Aesthetic Expression, Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities, Altruism, Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity, Appreciation of Teamwork, Appreciation of Productive Work, Bravery, Control of Feelings and Emotions, Cooperation, Courtesy, Curiosity, Democratic Decision-Making, Devotion, Discipline, Dignity of Manual Labour, Empathy, Environmental Awareness, Faithfulness, Friendship, Frugality in Resource Consumption, Gender Equality, Generosity, Gratitude, Health Consciousness, Honesty, Joy of Giving, Justice, Kindness to Animals and Insects, Kindness to Humans, Leadership, Learning to Live Together, Love for Family, Love for Society, Modesty, Multiculturalism, National Consciousness, Non-Acceptance of Untouchability, Non-Violence, Persistence, Positive Thinking, Punctuality, Quest for Knowledge, Religious Tolerance, Respect for Mother Tongue, Self-Confidence, Self-Dignity, Sense of Equality, Simplicity in Conduct and Wants, Social Responsibility, Sympathy, Tolerance, Trust, Truthfulness, and Unity.

FINDINGS FROM THE ANALYSIS

Researcher analyzed 16 Bengali textbooks used for Classes I to VIII over the past two decades, comparing textbooks published before and after 2011.

- New Textbooks (After 2011): 34 out of 54 identified values were reflected.
- Old Textbooks (Before 2011): 26 out of 54 identified values were present.
- Common Values in Both Old and New Textbooks (20 values):
These values appeared consistently in both sets of textbooks: Aesthetic Expression, Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities, Appreciation of Cultural Diversity, Appreciation

of Group Work, Bravery, Courtesy, Dignity of Manual Labour, Empathy, Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, Health Consciousness, Kindness to Living Beings, Love for Family, Love for Society, National Consciousness, Punctuality, Quest for Knowledge, Respect and Love for Mother Tongue, Self-Confidence, and Unity.

- Values Present in Old Textbooks but Missing in New Textbooks (6 values): These values were emphasized before 2011 but are absent in newer textbooks: Frugality in Resource Consumption, Persistence, Religious Tolerance, Self-Dignity, Sense of Equality, and Tolerance.
- Values Newly Introduced in New Textbooks (14 values): These values were added to textbooks after 2011 and were not present earlier – (Altruism, Cooperation, Curiosity, Democratic Decision-Making, Devotion, Discipline, Gender Equality, Honesty, Learning to Live Together, Modesty, Non-Acceptance of Untouchability, Positive Thinking, Simplicity in Conduct and Wants, and Truthfulness.)

The analysis reveals a shift in value emphasis in Bengali textbooks before and after 2011. While some values remained consistent, several older values were omitted, and new values were introduced in updated textbooks. These changes indicate a possible transformation in educational priorities and societal expectations reflected in the curriculum.

HUMAN VALUES IN ACCORDANCE WITH CHANGE IN AGE GROUP:

According to Notification No. 978-SE (EE)/10M-186/2010, dated 16.11.2016, issued by the School Education Department, Elementary Education Branch, Government of West Bengal, the appropriate age for each elementary class is as follows:

Table No - 1: Age Appropriate class for elementary students

Class	Year
Class- I	above 6 years to less than 7 years
Class- II	above 7 years to less than 8 years
Class- III	above 8 years to less than 9 years
Class- IV	above 9 years to less than 10 years
Class- V	above 10 years to less than 11 years
Class- VI	above 11 years to less than 12 years
Class- VII	above 12 years to less than 13 years
Class- VIII	above 13 years to less than 14 years

This classification confirms that each class is structured based on students' age groups. Therefore, it can be assumed that textbooks are designed in alignment with these age divisions to ensure students receive age-appropriate learning materials.

Grouping of Classes and Learning Outcomes

As per the Draft Report on Curriculum and Syllabus (2011), Government of West Bengal, the eight elementary classes (I–VIII) have been categorized into four groups, with each group consisting of two consecutive classes:

- **Group 1:** Classes **I & II**
- **Group 2:** Classes **III & IV**
- **Group 3:** Classes **V & VI**
- **Group 4:** Classes **VII & VIII**

Since each group consists of two classes, it is evident that the curriculum is structured to cater to the common learning needs of students within the same age bracket. The learning outcomes for each group are defined accordingly.

Human Values Reflected in Textbooks across Age Groups

Textbooks for each age group (two-class groups) were analyzed to identify human values embedded in the content. These values were categorized based on their presence across different age levels, helping to understand how values are emphasized and developed progressively throughout elementary education. This analysis provides a comprehensive view of how human values are integrated into textbooks, ensuring that students receive age-appropriate moral and ethical education.

Table 2: Human Values Reflected in Bengali Textbooks for Age Group I (Above 6 to Less Than 8 Years, Classes I & II)

Reflected Values (Old Textbooks)	Reflected Values (New Textbooks)
Aesthetic Expression	Aesthetic Expression
Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity	Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity
Appreciation of Group Working	Appreciation of Group Working
Environmental Awareness	Environmental Awareness
National Consciousness	National Consciousness
Dignity of Manual Labour	Affirmation of Positive Qualities
Fraternity	Devotion
Frugality in Consumption of Resources	Discipline
Health Consciousness	Democratic Decision-Making
Kindness to Living Beings	Learning to Live Together
Love for Family	Truthfulness
Empathy	Altruism
Quest for Knowledge	-
Self-Confidence	-

Table 3: Human Values Reflected in Bengali Textbooks for Age Group II (Above 6 to Less Than 8 Years, Classes III & IV)

Reflected Values (Old Textbooks)	Reflected Values (New Textbooks)
Aesthetic Expression	Aesthetic Expression
Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity	Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity
Bravery	Bravery
Dignity of Manual Labour	Dignity of Manual Labour
Environmental Awareness	Environmental Awareness
Fraternity	Fraternity
Kindness to Living Beings	Kindness to Living Beings
National Consciousness	National Consciousness
Persistence	Appreciation of Group Working
Punctuality	Health Consciousness
Quest for Knowledge	Quest for Knowledge
Religious Tolerance	Learning to Live Together
Self-Dignity	Cooperation
-	Positive Thinking
-	Curiosity
-	Truthfulness
-	Unity

Table 4: Human Values Reflected in Bengali Textbooks for Age Group III (Above 6 to Less Than 8 Years, Classes V & VI)

Reflected Values (Old Textbooks)	Reflected Values (New Textbooks)
Bravery	Learning to Live Together
Environmental Awareness	Environmental Awareness
Fraternity	Fraternity
Kindness to Living Beings	Kindness to Living Beings
National Consciousness	National Consciousness
Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities	Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities
Aesthetic Expression	Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity
Religious Tolerance	Gender Equality
Unity	Positive Thinking
-	Quest for Knowledge

Table 5 : Human Values Reflected in Bengali Textbooks for Age Group IV (Above 6 to Less Than 8 Years, Classes VII & VIII)

Reflected Values (Old Textbooks)	Reflected Values (New Textbooks)
Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities	Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities
Courtesy	Courtesy
Environmental Awareness	Environmental Awareness
Fraternity	Fraternity
National Consciousness	National Consciousness
Respect and Love for Mother Tongue	Respect and Love for Mother Tongue
Kindness to Living Beings	Kindness to Living Beings
Love for Family	Love for Family
Love for Society	Love for Society
Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity	Aesthetic Expression
Sense of Equality	Gender Equality
Tolerance	Honesty
-	Altruism
-	Dignity of Manual Labour
-	Empathy
-	Modesty
-	Cooperation
-	Non-Acceptance of Untouchability
-	Punctuality
-	Quest for Knowledge
-	Devotion
-	Self-Confidence

FINDINGS FROM THE ANALYSIS

- Common Values in Both Old and New Textbooks:**
Aesthetic Expression, Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity, Bravery, Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, Kindness to Living Beings, National Consciousness, Quest for Knowledge, Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities, Love for Family, Love for Society, Courtesy, Respect and Love for Mother Tongue.
- Values Present in Old Textbooks but Missing in New Textbooks:**
Dignity of Manual Labour (for younger age groups), Frugality in Consumption of Resources, Persistence, Religious Tolerance, Self-Dignity, Sense of Equality, Tolerance.

- **New Values introduced in New Textbooks:**

Affirmation of Positive Qualities, Devotion, Discipline, Democratic Decision-Making, Learning to Live Together, Truthfulness, Altruism, Cooperation, Positive Thinking, Curiosity, Unity, Gender Equality, Honesty, Modesty, Non-Acceptance of Untouchability, Punctuality, Empathy, Self-Confidence.

Table 6 : Age Group-Wise Comparison of Human Values in Old and New Textbooks

(This table highlights the similarities, removals, and additions of values across different age groups in old and new textbooks.)

Age Group	Common Values (Present in Both Old & New Textbooks)	Values Removed (Present in Old but Missing in New Textbooks)	Newly Introduced Values (Present in New but Missing in Old Textbooks)
Above 6 to Less than 8 Years (Class I & II)	Aesthetic Expression, Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity, Appreciation of Group Work, Environmental Awareness, National Consciousness	Dignity of Manual Labour, Fraternity, Frugality in Consumption of Resources, Health Consciousness, Kindness to Living Beings, Quest for Knowledge, Self-Confidence	Affirmation of Positive Qualities, Devotion, Discipline, Democratic Decision-Making, Learning to Live Together, Truthfulness, Altruism
Above 8 to Less than 10 Years (Class III & IV)	Aesthetic Expression, Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity, Bravery, Dignity of Manual Labour, Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, Kindness to Living Beings, National Consciousness, Quest for Knowledge	Persistence, Punctuality, Religious Tolerance, Self-Dignity	Appreciation of Group Work, Health Consciousness, Learning to Live Together, Cooperation, Positive Thinking, Curiosity, Truthfulness, Unity
Above 10 to Less than 12 Years (Class V & VI)	Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, Kindness to Living Beings, National Consciousness, Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities	Aesthetic Expression, Religious Tolerance, Unity	Learning to Live Together, Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity, Gender Equality, Positive Thinking, Quest for Knowledge

Age Group	Common Values (Present in Both Old & New Textbooks)	Values Removed (Present in Old but Missing in New Textbooks)	Newly Introduced Values (Present in New but Missing in Old Textbooks)
Above 12 to Less than 14 Years (Class VII & VIII)	Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities, Courtesy, Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, National Consciousness, Respect and Love for Mother Tongue, Kindness to Living Beings, Love for Family, Love for Society	Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity, Sense of Equality, Tolerance	Aesthetic Expression, Gender Equality, Honesty, Altruism, Dignity of Manual Labour, Empathy, Modesty, Cooperation, Non-Acceptance of Untouchability, Punctuality, Quest for Knowledge, Devotion, Self-Confidence

FINDINGS FROM THE ANALYSIS

1. *Values Retained Across All Age Groups:*

Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, Kindness to Living Beings, National Consciousness, Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities were consistently present in both old and new textbooks.

2. *Values Removed in New Textbooks (Previously Present in Old Textbooks):*

Early Age Groups (6–8 years & 8–10 years): Removed values include *Dignity of Manual Labour, Frugality in Consumption of Resources, Religious Tolerance, Self-Dignity, and Tolerance*.

Older Age Groups (10–14 years): *Religious Tolerance, Sense of Equality, and Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity* were no longer emphasized.

3. *New Values Introduced in New Textbooks:*

For Younger Students (6–10 years): *Affirmation of Positive Qualities, Devotion, Discipline, Democratic Decision-Making, Learning to Live Together, Truthfulness, Altruism, Cooperation, Positive Thinking, Curiosity, Unity*.

For Older Students (10–14 years): *Gender Equality, Honesty, Empathy, Modesty, Cooperation, Non-Acceptance of Untouchability, Punctuality, Quest for Knowledge, Devotion, Self-Confidence*.

4. *Shift in Focus:*

Older Textbooks (Before 2011): Focused more on *Dignity of Manual Labour, Religious Tolerance, Persistence, Frugality, Self-Dignity, and Tolerance*.

Newer Textbooks (After 2011): Placed greater emphasis on *Democratic Decision-Making, Cooperation, Gender Equality, Positive Thinking, Learning to Live Together, Non-Acceptance of Untouchability, and Empathy*.

The comparison of human values across age groups reveals a significant shift in focus from traditional ethical values (e.g., dignity of labour, religious tolerance, and frugality) to more modern social values (e.g., gender equality, cooperation, positive thinking and democratic decision-making).

COMPARISON OF HUMAN VALUES IN OLD AND NEW TEXTBOOKS ACROSS AGE GROUPS

Age Group 1 (6–8 years)

In the textbooks designed for students aged 6 to 8 years (Classes I & II), the old textbooks contained a total of 14 values, whereas the new textbooks contained 12 values. Among these, only five values were common between the two versions. These shared values include Aesthetic Expression, Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity, Appreciation of Group Work, Environmental Awareness, and National Consciousness. This indicates that while certain foundational values remained unchanged in both versions, the new textbooks introduced some new values while removing others.

Age Group 2 (8–10 years)

For students in the 8 to 10 years age group (Classes III & IV), the old textbooks reflected 13 values, whereas the new textbooks included 17 values. Among these, eight values were common in both versions. These shared values were Aesthetic Expression, Appreciation and Respect for Cultural Diversity, Bravery, Dignity of Manual Labour, Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, Kindness to Living Beings, and National Consciousness. The increase in the number of values in the new textbooks suggests an expanded emphasis on moral and ethical development at this stage. The introduction of new values in this age group indicates a shift towards instilling additional social and interpersonal qualities in students.

Age Group 3 (10–12 years)

In the textbooks used for students aged 10 to 12 years (Classes V & VI), the old textbooks contained 9 values, whereas the new textbooks contained 10 values. Among these, five values remained the same in both versions. These shared values were learning to Live Together, Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, Kindness to Living Beings, and National Consciousness. While the number of values remained relatively stable in this age group, the shift in focus suggests that certain values were either replaced or newly introduced to align with changing educational priorities.

Age Group 4 (12–14 years)

For students in the 12 to 14 years age group (Classes VII & VIII), there was a significant increase in the number of values in new textbooks compared to the old ones. The old textbooks contained 12 values, whereas the new textbooks reflected 22 values. Among these, nine values were found to be common across both versions. These shared values were – Affirmation of Others' Positive Qualities, Courtesy, Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, National Consciousness, Respect and Love for Mother Tongue, Kindness to Living Beings, Love for Family, and Love for Society. The substantial increase in the number of values in the new textbooks for this age group suggests a greater emphasis on social, ethical, and moral development as students approach adolescence.

FINDINGS FROM THE ANALYSIS

1. Increase in the Number of Values in New Textbooks

The total number of values increased significantly in the new textbooks, especially in the 8–10 years and 12–14 years age groups. The most noticeable expansion occurred in Age Group 4 (12–14 years), where the number of values almost doubled from 12 to 22. This reflects an educational shift towards providing students with a broader moral and ethical foundation in their later years of elementary education.

2. Reduction of Values in Early Age Groups (6–8 years)

While the total number of values increased overall, the 6–8 years age group saw a slight reduction from 14 values in the old textbooks to 12 values in the new ones. This suggests that the curriculum for younger children might have been streamlined to focus on fewer but more essential values at an early stage.

3. Retention of Core Values across All Age Groups

Certain values were consistently present in both the old and new textbooks across all age groups. These include Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, National Consciousness, and Kindness to Living Beings. The continued emphasis on these values indicates that they are considered fundamental for moral education and character development throughout elementary schooling.

4. Shift in the Emphasis of Human Values

- In the old textbooks, there was a stronger focus on traditional ethical values, such as Dignity of Manual Labour, Religious Tolerance, and Tolerance.
- In the new textbooks, there was a greater emphasis on modern values, including Democratic Decision-Making, Cooperation, Truthfulness, Positive Thinking, Gender Equality, and Non-Acceptance of Untouchability.
- This shift reflects an updated educational approach that aligns with contemporary social and cultural values, fostering a more inclusive and progressive learning environment.

The comparison of human values in old and new textbooks highlights a notable shift in educational priorities over time. While certain core values have remained constant, the new textbooks have introduced additional values that emphasize social responsibility, ethical awareness, and inclusivity. The significant increase in values in later age groups (8–14 years) suggests a greater effort to instill broader moral principles as students grow older. This change may indicate that modern educational reforms aim to prepare students for a more diverse, cooperative, and ethically conscious society, reflecting evolving societal needs and expectations.

CONCLUSION

The transition from old textbooks (pre-2011) to new textbooks (post-2011) in West Bengal reflects a paradigm shift in the emphasis on human values in elementary education. While core values such as Environmental Awareness, Fraternity, National Consciousness, and Kindness to Living Beings remain consistent across both versions, significant changes in value priorities can be observed.

In old textbooks, there was a stronger focus on traditional ethical and moral values, such as Dignity of Manual Labour, Religious Tolerance, Persistence, and Tolerance. These values emphasized discipline, respect for work, and ethical living. However, in new textbooks, there is a noticeable shift towards modern social and interpersonal values, including Democratic Decision-Making, Cooperation, Gender Equality, Positive Thinking, and Non-Acceptance of Untouchability. This change indicates a broader emphasis on inclusivity, social awareness, and progressive thinking in education.

Additionally, while early age groups (6–8 years) saw a slight reduction in the number of values, older age groups (12–14 years) experienced a significant increase in values, suggesting a structured and gradual moral development approach. The new curriculum aligns with contemporary societal expectations, preparing students to be more socially responsible, ethically aware, and inclusive citizens.

This paradigm shift highlights the evolution of educational priorities from a discipline-based approach in old textbooks to a value-driven, socially inclusive framework in new textbooks.

The Importance of Value Education in Bengali Vernacular Textbooks

In today's world, value education has gained more significance than ever before. Societies across the globe are facing a crisis of values, where issues such as moral degradation, social injustice, and ethical conflicts are becoming increasingly prevalent. Without instilling strong moral values in individuals, achieving social justice, peace, happiness, and social order remains an unattainable ideal. Value education plays a crucial role in shaping the hopes, aspirations, and ethical foundations of a nation, contributing to the overall progress of society.

Value education is not a one-time process but a continuous practice that must begin from early childhood. Therefore, Bengali vernacular textbooks at the elementary level play an essential role in fostering human values among young learners. Teachers, as facilitators of knowledge, must emphasize value-based education while teaching these textbooks, ensuring that students internalize and practice these values in their daily lives. Elementary education serves as the foundation for shaping a child's character and moral compass, making it a critical stage for value development.

The Role of Vernacular Textbooks in Value Education

Human values are essential tools for leading a meaningful life, and in an era of value crisis, their practice has become more relevant than ever. Bengali language and literature textbooks play a crucial role in shaping children's moral development, as young minds are highly impressionable. Due to their "tabula rasa" (blank slate) nature, children are naturally imaginative and can be molded with the desired ethical principles.

The inclusion of new values such as altruism, cooperation, curiosity, discipline, truthfulness, learning to live together, and positive thinking in new Bengali textbooks provides students with a strong ethical foundation. These values encourage them to engage in acts of kindness, teamwork, and service to humanity, fostering responsible and compassionate future citizens.

However, value education should not be limited to textbooks alone. Teachers must go beyond the curriculum and actively integrate values into students' lives through discussions, activities, and

real-life applications. If these values remain confined to books without being practiced in daily life, the entire purpose of value education through vernacular textbooks will be lost. Only by embedding these values into students' thinking and behavior can we ensure that they grow into morally upright and responsible citizens who contribute positively to society.

REFERENCES

- Aggarwal, J. C. (1984). *Landmarks in the history of modern Indian education*. New Delhi: Vani Educational Book.
- Aggarwal, J. C. (2006). *Education for values, environment, and human rights*. Delhi: Shipra Publication.
- Biswas, A., Sinha, R., & Guha, A. (2018). Human values reflected in Bengali textbooks at the elementary level in West Bengal. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*. Retrieved from http://ijrar.com/upload_issue/ijrar_issue_20542481.pdf
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education*. New York: Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research* (4th ed.). New Delhi: PHI Learning Private Limited.
- Flick, U. (2014). *An introduction to qualitative research*. New Delhi: Sage.
- Khastagir, A. (2006). *Bangla primar sangraha (1816-1855)*. Kolkata: Paschim Banga Bangla Akademi.
- National Council of Educational Research and Training. (2002). *National curriculum framework-2002*. New Delhi: NCERT.
- National Council of Educational Research and Training. (2007). *National curriculum framework-2005*. New Delhi: NCERT.
- Neuendorf, K. (2002). *The content analysis guidebook*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications. Retrieved from http://depts.washington.edu/methods/readings/Neuendorf_2002.pdf
- Poschim Banga Sarkar. (1979). *Prathomik sikshar odhikar: Prathomik sikshar sikshakrom o pathysuchi*. (In Bengali).
- Sharada, A., & Prasad, D. (2012). Human values in English textbooks at the school level: A study. In N. R. Kishan (Ed.), *Value education: Issues and challenges* (p. 6). New Delhi: A.P.H. Publishing Corporation.